

Quantum Features from Time-Independence of Impulse Balance in the Photon Reflection/Refraction Problem

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If one considers the reflection/refraction of a steady stream of photons moving in the positive x direction and striking an $n_1=1$ versus n_2 interface along the y axis at $x=0$, one may immediately write a conservation of photon number equation i.e. $N(\text{incoming}) = N(\text{reflected}) + N(\text{refracted})$ ((1)). This equation, however, does not shed any light on the ratio of $N(\text{reflected})$ to $N(\text{refracted})$ for a given $N(\text{incoming})$. One may also notice that no information about the index of refraction is included. This information manifests itself in: $E = p_1 c/n_1 = p_2 c/n_2$.

Taking ((1)) and multiplying by e (photon energy) yields a conservation of energy equation. In both the cases of photon number and energy conservation there is no notion of flux. Taking the energy conservation equation and writing $e=p_1c_1$ or $e=p_2c_2$ yields an equation relating momenta (proportional to impulses), but this equation involves dynamics i.e. fluxes i.e. c_1, c_2 values. Thus it is not on the same footing as the photon number or energy conservation equations.

We argue that there should exist an impulse balance type equation which does not depend on flux. We suggest this is a key physical idea. (For example, the two-slit interference pattern of $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ are the same.) As a result, the single equation ((1)) is not sufficient for solving the problem. To solve the problem, one needs to recast ((1)) in terms of flux (a notion which exists classically) divided by c_i (speed of light) so that one obtains the number of photons. By having $1/c_1$ appear in the equation, one may multiply by e so that $e/c_i = p_i$.

One then has the equation: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ ((2)) where AA =incoming flux, BB =reflected flux and CC refracted flux. One must change from a static picture of counting photons to a flux picture, but divide fluxes by c_i 's to regain the static picture. Incoming flux is written as AA to indicate it is positive etc. ((2)) still does not solve for B and C in terms of A and n_1, n_2 , but one may bring BB/c_1 to the LHS and break ((2)) into two equations using differences of squares. Thus one has an $A+B=C$ equation which is like a nonflux balance of probability or energy (if one multiplies by e) and a static momentum/impulse balance equation $p_A - p_B = p_2 C$. Solving the problem involves creating not only time independent photon number/energy balance, but also time-independent photon momentum/impulse balance.

We argue that the breaking of ((2)) into two equations introduces the notion of quantum mechanics because one uses "square roots" of flux probability. One may ask why one does not simply find a second equation in addition to the photon number/energy balance equation. We argue that the single number balance equation contains all of the necessary information in the problem i.e. flux, photon number, energy or p 's and c 's. Thus a second equation would not be independent. As a result, one must break the single photon balance equation into two independent equations leading to a different kind of physical balance i.e. one involving square roots of fluxes instead of fluxes i.e. quantum mechanics.

Photon Number and Energy Conservation in Reflection/Refraction

A single photon moving in the positive x direction and hitting an $n_1=1$ versus $n_2>n_1$ (for example) interface along the y axis either reflects or refracts. The photon number is preserved as is its energy e . The single photon problem may also be considered in terms of a steady stream picture.

Classically one may immediately write a conservation of photon number equation:

$$N(\text{incoming}) = N(\text{reflected}) + N(\text{refracted}) \quad ((3))$$

where N is the number of photons, a positive integer. Multiplying ((3)) by e yields a conservation of energy equation. Both of these demonstrate no dynamics. Multiplying by $e=pc$ to create a momentum type balance, however, introduces both c_1 and c_2 , the speeds of light in $n_1=1$ and n_2 . Thus ((3)) is associated with a momentum balance provided dynamics are included. Thus ((3)) treats number and energy statically, but momentum dynamically.

We note that ((3)) does not shed any light on the ratio of $N(\text{reflected})$ versus $N(\text{refracted})$ for a given $N(\text{incoming})$. Furthermore it contains no information about c_1, c_2 or p_1, p_2 which is essential information in the problem. We argue, however, that there is another essential problem with ((3)), namely that it presents a static conservation of photon number equation, a static energy conservation equation if multiplied by e , but a dynamic momentum conservation type equation. Thus, if one were to argue that one should have balances of number, energy and momentum at static level, the single equation ((3)) does not provide this.

As a first step, one may introduce c_1 and c_2 by writing $N = AA/c_i$ where AA is flux and c photon speed. Then ((3)) becomes:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((4))$$

AA represents the incoming stream, BB the reflected and CC the refracted. AA is used to indicate that flux is a positive number. ((4)), however, still does not solve for B and C in terms of A . The asymmetry between ((4)) and ((4)) multiplied by e and the p momentum situation still exists. For photon number and energy one has a flux divided by a velocity c_i i.e. the ratio of two dynamic quantities. Multiplying ((4)) by e and using $e=pc$, however, removes the ratio of dynamic quantities. Thus even though p for a particle with rest mass may be thought of as containing dynamics i.e. mv (nonrelativistically) or $mv/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ (relativistically), p actually delivers an impulse hit which is velocity independent i.e. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$.

Problems with ((4))

We suggest that the classical conservation equation ((4)) (written in terms of dynamics) seems to have two problems.

((A)) It is one equation and there are two unknowns

((B)) It treats photon number and energy conservation statically, but momentum balance dynamically.

We suggest that ((A) and ((B)) are essentially the same problem. It seems one equation cannot yield static balance type form for particle number/probability, energy and momentum. Rather two separate equations are needed. ((4)), however, is a completely correct photon number conservation equation, and contains information about energy and momentum as well thus these two equations should combine to yield ((4)).

Solution to Problems with ((4))

As noted in (1), a solution to the problems with ((4)) is to bring $BB/c1$ to the LHS and use differences of squares to write two equations i.e.

$$A+B = C \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p1A - p1B = p2C \quad ((5b))$$

Both of these have the appearance of static balance equations, i.e. no dynamics appear. ((5a)) may be thought of as a kind of probability balance (and multiplied by e as a static energy balance) and ((5b)) as a static momentum balance. ((5a)) and ((5b)) may then be solved to find B, C in terms of $A, n1$ and $n2$ as shown in (1).

Thus we argue that the motivation of breaking ((4)) into two equations is to have photon number, energy and impulse/momentum balance all represented statically i.e. with no dynamics.

Why Should Momentum Impulse be Represented by a Static Balance ((5b))?

In classical statistical mechanics, one does not use momentum/impulse balance, but rather pressure balance. This involves writing $2p = \text{impulse}$ multiplied by p/m i.e. velocity or flux. This accounts for the fact that one has many particles with p, v and so wishes to compute force per second. In the photon reflection/refraction problem, one may think of a single photon in terms of probabilities to reflect/refract and wish for a nonflux based balance of impulse in terms of probability.

We argue that this idea of static impulse balance (even though there are dynamics in the problem i.e. ci) leads to a basic idea of quantum mechanics. For example, when considering two slit interference, one does not consider flux only $\exp(ipx)$. One may have $p = m1v1 = m2v2$, but these produce the same pattern which does not depend on dynamics.

A second argument is that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$, which is both the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical actions with $v = x/t$, naturally separates t and x . $dA/dx = p$ or creating an eigenvalue equation: $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. In such a treatment, dynamics do not appear. P represents an impulse in the free particle quantum mechanics approach.

Why Not Seek an Extra Equation to the Photon Number/Energy Balance One?

The photon number balance equation (which when multiplied by e is also an energy balance equation) is a perfectly fine equation. The fact that there are two unknowns and only one equation, might suggest one simply look for another independent equation containing A, B, C . One might even consider some kind of equation involving momentum/impulse appearing statically. The issue with this idea is that the photon balance equation when multiplied by e already contains information about p . The problem is that the equation is dynamic due to the fluxes. Thus an additional static equation balancing momenta would not be independent of the photon number balance equation. In particular, it seems that the photon number balance equation contains information about fluxes, number and energy balance and information about p (momentum) as well. In other words, all of the necessary information of the problem is contained in this one equation except for the two problems mentioned above. To resolve the issue, one does not then seek another equation as it would not be independent, but rather tries to break up the single conservation of photon number equation. This has consequences in that it leads to two equations in A, B, C rather than AA, BB, CC , i.e. the square root of fluxes (i.e. probabilities) appear which is a quantum feature.

Thus given two equations, one may always multiply the two LHS sides together and equate it to the product of the two RHS (etc), to obtain one equation. This process, however, seems to lose information as the two equations may be used to solve for two unknowns, while the single one cannot. Given a single equation which makes physical sense i.e. photon conservation, one may need to break it into two equivalent equations which also have physical meaning, although different from the combined case. Thus there are two sets of physical balances, the ‘square root’ one, implying the photon/number conservation one, but also vice versa. The fact that the photon number balance equation cannot treat momentum in a static manner, but contains momentum information, implies one must somehow “break out” a static momentum equation from the photon balance one. This idea is enhanced by the presence of two unknowns in one equation which seemingly has all of the information needed to solve the problem.

Conclusion

In conclusion, $e=pc$ for a photon treats e and p in different manners. If one has a static equation for e , replacing e with pc yields a dynamic equation, i.e. one containing c_i values if there are more than one. This is exactly the situation for energy or photon number conservation in a reflection/refraction problem. Furthermore, a single photon number/energy conservation equation is not sufficient for finding the ratio of reflected to scattered photons in terms of the number of incoming ones. A second equation is needed. We argue that physically this second equation is associated with a static balance of p (momentum/impulse) which cannot appear together in the same equation for a static balance of energy/photon number. Thus one may begin with a conservation of photon energy equation written in terms of dynamical quantities: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ (AA, BB and CC represent fluxes of the incoming, reflected and refracted photons). One may next create two equations by bringing BB/c_1 to the LHS and using differences of squares. These two equations may be used to solve for B, C in terms of A and n_1, n_2 . We argue that the motivation for this breakup is to obtain two equations. The first is a probability (or energy if multiplied by e) balance which is static and the second is a

momentum/impulse balance which is also static. It is not possible, it seems, to have all three appearing statically in the same conservation equation because $e=pc$.

We also note that the single photon number or energy balance equation seems to contain all of the information needed to solve the reflection/refraction problem, but there are two unknowns and only one equation. It thus does not seem to make sense to seek a second equation because it would not be independent of the first. This implies that the photon balance equation should be broken into two equations. This approach allows for two equations, but also for a static balance of probability, energy and momentum which is not possible in a single number/energy balance equation because $e=pc$ i.e. e is static, but pc is not due to the presence of c .

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Information, Quantum Probability and Reflection/Refraction (preprint, zenodo, 2022)